

TARNAS - TARNAS: A Tool for Translating and Abstracting RNA Secondary Structures

version 1

TARNAS can be applied in three scenarios

1. RNA secondary structure translations
2. Deleting or retaining comments, blank lines, and headers of the file
3. Abstracting RNA secondary structures into three views: Core, Core Plus and Shape

If you use TARNAS, please cite use using the references at

<https://github.com/bdslab/TARNAS/blob/main/README.md>

Accepted Input file formats for RNA secondary structures

TARNAS supports RNA secondary structure in different formats, including:

- BPSEQ format, with or without header information
- CT format, with or without header information
- (Extended) Dot-Bracket Notation, with or without header information
- (Extended) Dot-Bracket Notation without sequence (only structure), with or without header information
- Arc Annotated Sequence (AAS), with or without header information
- Arc Annotated Sequence (AAS) without sequence (only structure), with or without header information
- FASTA, with or without header information
- RNAML

TARNAS is distributed as standalone desktop and web application

The web application is available at <https://bdslab.unicam.it/tarnas/> and processes one molecule at a time.

The standalone desktop application is available at <https://github.com/bdslab/TARNAS> and it is distributed with two executable jar files

- TARNAS_CLI.jar and

- TARNAS.jar (TARNAS version with GUI)

Installation

Download the zip file of last version of TARNAS from folder "download" at

<https://github.com/bdslab/TARNAS>

and put it in any position of your drive.

Unzip the file with the facilities of your operating system. The folder TARNAS-<1.0.0> is created containing the following files:

- TARNAS.jar --- executable jar for GUI version of TARNAS
- TARNAS_CLI.jar --- executable jar for CLI version of TARNAS
- examples --- folder containing TranslationExamples, Abstractions and Quantitative Features
- INSTALL.txt --- information on TARNAS installation
- README.md --- TARNAS description and usage information
- COPYING.txt --- copyright information
- LICENSE --- full GNU GPL Version 3 License
- CHANGELOG.txt --- information about the evolution of TARNAS versions

The executable jar files runs on every Linux, Windows and Mac OS platform in which a Java SE Runtime Environment 19 is installed.

For information and installing the Java Runtime Environment see
<http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/java/javase/downloads/index.html>

The source code and JAR files for both versions of TARNAS can also be found in the Releases section of the GitHub repository.

Using TARNAS_CLI

Open a terminal window of your operating system and use the change directory (cd) command to move to a folder in which the executable jar(s) and the configuration file(s) were placed. To launch the basic TARNAS comparator digit:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar [--zip=<zipFileName>] <inputPath>  
<outputPathFold> [COMMAND]
```

The following [COMMAND] can be used:

- translate Translate the input to the specified destination format.
- cleaning Cleans the input based on the selected cleaning option
- abstractions Computes abstractions of the input RNA file. By default, it computes core, coreplus and shape abstractions.

The command for translating is

```
TARNAS_CLI.jar [--zip=<zipFileName>] <inputPath> <outputPathFold>  
translate [-hV] [--no-header] [--non-canonical-pairs] [--statistics]  
<destinationFormat>
```

The command for cleaning is

```
TARNAS_CLI.jar cleaning [-hV] [--comments] [--empty] [--merge]  
[--lines=<stringToBeRemoved>]
```

The command for generating abstractions is

```
TARNAS_CLI.jar abstractions [-hV] [--core] [--core-plus] [--shape]
```